

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING INTEGRATED METHODS IN TEACHING MUSIC

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ABSTRACT

Music teachers are increasingly using technology to develop new strategies to engage students. Where once we considered acoustic instruments, pens and paper as the main teaching aids, now with the help of technologies such as the iPad and educational programs, it is possible to engage students in the creative study of music. the effectiveness of which is discussed.

The development and transformation of our country is an urgent need of all young people. The upbringing of young people who are strong, educated, proud of their homeland is one of the most important issues of our time. This is one of the most complex and wide-ranging problems in education.

It is known that music education, along with other disciplines, information technology is closely linked with IT. Music teachers are also using IT technology to increase student learning and engagement because it has more sophisticated and user-friendly technology.

Indeed, while the specifics of using music as a teaching tool vary depending on the teacher and the resources of a particular audience, the overall evolution of music education tools and technology is evidenced by several key trends. Music technology usually encourages the sharing of music on a large scale. This trend can be seen in music and educational tools such as Soundtrap or

Google Classroom, as well as on wider multimedia social platforms such as YouTube and others.

Music education tools have emerged that offer additional practice to complement classroom learning with specific skills, such as ear training apps that help students learn how to adjust volume. These tools open up opportunities for self-study and allow teachers to focus on other key skills.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Technology is just a tool, and a tool will not be useful unless it understands the different ways it can be used to achieve a particular result in a particular context. If music teachers want to effectively integrate technology into teaching, learning, and evaluation, more is needed than understanding specific technological tools. As a result, when learning to use technology with students, it is important for music teachers to consider targeted learning objectives, advantages and limitations of the technology under consideration,

teaching and learning strategies to be applied, and context.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Targeted and strategic music teachers can enhance their education to engage students and teach different aspects of music creation and production.

For example, digital media has changed the way many artists create, produce, and distribute music. Some researchers have used this to explore the benefits of platforms such as YouTube, as well as the possibilities of using informal music education to complement learning in a formal learning environment.

However, the best way to integrate technology into teaching is to vary significantly depending on the goal and the needs of the students. For example, if many students are struggling to master a particular skill, showing other teachers video lessons can help deepen the lesson. It may take some experience to determine what is most appropriate for the audience, but mastering the technology is a clear goal and continuous improvement thinking can ultimately improve students' learning pathways.

Technology has the potential to transform music and music lessons and share them more widely with others. Smart music teachers use these opportunities to increase their students' activity in creating, performing, and listening to music.

In addition to covering a wide range of music genres, the syllabus of the program explores advanced concepts in the psychology, music design, and technology of music education in a music classroom. The faculty includes teachers of various professional disciplines, from professional musicians to internationally recognized music education researchers and authors.

Here are the top 5 reasons why music education can be beneficial for our students:

- The music education program gives its students an aesthetic experience.
- Music education instills "life values" in students. Some of them include; builds discipline, collaboration, social skills, and good character.
- Knowledge of music technology, music history, music theory and music culture reinforces knowledge in other disciplines.
- Music often creates a sense of school spirit, which in turn gives students a sense of self-worth, which almost always reflects a positive attitude.

Promoting the arts is what our students need to excel in all aspects of life.

A person who studies composition is a person who wants to create his own music and at the same time decides to act independently in many cases. Whether it's about independent new works for a concert hall, music in a medial context, or an artistic statement on a released audio medium, composers are always in a very ambitious environment that faces equally high artistic and technical requirements.

Methods and their importance in music education.

Imitation forms the student's repertoire of melody, rhythm, meter, tempo and dynamics. Students will master the basic musical materials for the "instrument box" for use in more complex lessons in the future.

The search method — students begin to understand and even apply what they have learned through imitation. They hear the movement of tones, the content of rhythms, the movement of the meter, and they learn the timbre of any instrument or sound they have access to. The Orff Instrumentarium

offers almost limitless possibilities for research.

After improvisation-research and imitation, students can not only understand, but also apply some possible combinations of rhythm and pitch, shape and dynamics, etc., in a musical context.

The use of information and communication technologies in music culture classes helps to develop the skills of active perception of music, to enrich children's musical experience, to absorb knowledge. This is an important condition for enriching the musical culture of schoolchildren in general. Therefore, the following tasks are important in the use of information and communication technologies in music education :

- Involve more students in music lessons in project activities.
- Expansion of the music cabinet library.
- learning new computer programs.

Here are some suggestions on how to use information and communication technologies in your music lessons:

-Student's role in the classroom needs to be changed;

- from a passive learner to an active participant in the learning process. In this case, the relationship between the student and the teacher changes towards a partnership, and the student becomes the subject of pedagogical activity from the object of pedagogical influence.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that in today's world, to increase the ability of young people to think independently, to involve them in more self-improvement, to use more information and communication technologies in the educational process, to teach young people music, art, it is very important to increase their interest in literature, theater and other types of art, to reveal their talents, to organize the effective use of computer technology and the Internet among the population and youth. All of these aspects allow young people to become mature musicians.

References:

1. Ishmuhamedov R.J., Yuldashev M. Innovative pedagogical technologies in education and upbringing.- T.: "Nihol" publishing house, 2013, 2016. - 279p.
2. Tolipov O., Usmonbaeva M. Applied bases of pedagogical technologies - T.: 2016. - 163 p.
3. Sayidahmedov NS New pedagogical technologies T.Moliya, 2013-172 p.
4. Tolipov O., Usmonbaeva M. Applied bases of pedagogical technologies - T.: 2016. - 163 p.
5. Urazova MB, Eshpulatov Sh.N. Design activity of the future teacher. // Methodical manual. - T.TSPU Risography, 2014. 6.5 p.
6. Nizomiy TSPU. The issue of teaching music in continuing education. -T.: 2019.